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D3 Paper on the performance of at least 8 commercially available X-ray dosimeter types in at least 3 NMIs/DIs covering different influence quantities, especially the defined clinically representative radiation qualities, enabling estimation of uncertainties related to air kerma measurements with different dosimeters

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1 Summary

The performance of commercially available diagnostic radiology dosimeters, including ionization chambers and solid-state detector-based X-ray multimeters, in terms of air kerma (rate) measurements was done. A total of 16 ionization chambers, covering 7 different ionization chamber models from different manufacturers, including detectors of different geometries such as spherical and plane-parallel, as well as different intended use, mostly covering radiography and mammography imaging modality applications, were included in the study. Also, the investigation was done on a total of 24 X-ray multimeters, covering 9 different device models, from different manufacturers. Therefore, the performance of 16 different diagnostic dosimeter models, which are commercially available, was investigated. The tests were performed in 14 NMIs and DIs using the harmonized measurement protocol, which covered several tests related to different influence quantities. The effects of measured value repeatability, dosimeter resolution, the effects of stabilization time, linearity, photon energy, angle of incidence (in two perpendicular planes, and rotation), and pulse duration on measured value were investigated. In this way the performance assessment regarding 8 relevant influence quantities was done. The data on dosimeter performance was acquired in the IEC 61267:2005 reference radiation fields, the RQR and RQT standard radiation quality series, in the X-ray tube voltage ranges from 40 kV to 150 kV and 100 kV to 150 kV, respectively. Also, the performance was evaluated in the non-standard copper-filtered radiation fields (CPRQs with 0.9 mm Cu added filtration to the selected established RQR radiation fields). The CPRQs are based on the previously identified clinically representative radiation qualities. The performance of the dosimeters was evaluated with respect to the IEC 61674:2024 standard. The observed performance test results can enable estimation of measurement uncertainties in terms of air kerma measurements with different diagnostic dosimeters. Based on the observed dosimeter performance, and the current limits of variation set for different influence quantities, a proposal to adjust the criteria was given. The newly proposed criteria have introduced distinct requirements for the reference-class and field-class dosimeters. The scientific publication titled "X-ray imaging dosimeter performance in standard and non-standard radiography radiation fields in terms of air kerma" presents the dosimeters examined, tests performed and observed performance, is provided in this report. The publication was submitted to a peer-reviewed journal. The publication has been published in the *Physica Medica* (European Journal of Medical Physics) scientific journal: Vol. 141; 105687; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmp.2025.105687>.

X-ray imaging dosimeter performance in standard and non-standard radiography radiation fields in terms of air kerma

Authors: Nikola Kržanović¹, Paula Toroi^{2,3,*}, Ivana Komatina^{1,4}, Bartel Jansen⁵, Argiro Boziari⁶, Margarida Caldeiraⁱ, Maysa Costa de Castro^{7,8}, Alessia Ciccotelli⁹, Ana Fernandes¹⁰, Andrea Kojić^{a,11}, Kam Lee¹², Carita Lindholm³, Stefan Pojtinger⁷, Erinc Reyhanoglu¹³, Luigi Rinaldi^{i,14}, Amra Šabeta¹⁵, Elisabeth Salomon^{16,7}, Sjarhei Saroka¹⁷, Claudia Silvestri⁹, Vladimir Sochor¹⁸, Viivi Valkama³, Jelena Vlahović^{1,19}, Miloš Živanović¹

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

For correspondence contact: Paula Toroi, Helsinki University Hospital Diagnostic Center, Radiology, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland; Address: Haartmaninkatu 4 00290 Helsinki; E-mail: paula.toroi@stuk.fi

¹ Vinca Institute of Nuclear Sciences – National Institute of Serbia, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

² Helsinki University Hospital Diagnostic Center, Radiology, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland

³ Radiation and Nuclear Safety Authority, Vantaa, Finland

⁴ Faculty of Physical Chemistry, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

⁵ Nationaal Metrologisch Instituut van Nederland, Delft, Netherlands

⁶ Elliniki Epitropi Atomikis Energeias, Athens, Greece

⁷ Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt, Braunschweig, Germany

⁸ Federal University of Pernambuco, Recife, Brazil

⁹ Istituto Nazionale di Metrologia delle Radiazioni Ionizzanti - Agenzia Nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile, Rome, Italy

¹⁰ Instituto Superior Técnico, Lisbon, Portugal

¹¹ Faculty of Physics, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

¹² Australian Radiation Protection and Nuclear Safety Agency, Victoria, Australia

¹³ Türkiye Enerji, Nükleer ve Maden Araştırma Kurumu, Ankara, Turkey

¹⁴ Scientific Institute for Research, Hospitalization and Health Care (IRCCS), Bambino Gesù Children's Hospital, Rome, Italy

¹⁵ Institut za mjeriteljstvo Bosne i Hercegovine, Sarajevo, Bosna i Hercegovina

¹⁶ Medical University of Vienna, Center for Medical Physics and Biomedical Engineering, Vienna, Austria

¹⁷ Institutul Național de Metrologie, Chisinau, Moldova

¹⁸ Cesky Metrologický Institut, Brno, Czech Republic

¹⁹ Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

2 Abstract

Introduction: X-ray medical imaging developments have introduced needs for updated dosimetry practices. *Methods:* Performance of commercially available dosimeters used for air kerma measurements in diagnostic and interventional radiology was examined. Ionization chambers and X-ray multimeters were tested in a wide range of air kerma rates, photon energies (using standard and non-standard radiation qualities), and angles of incidence with different dosimeter orientation and rotation. Stability and repeatability of the measured value, the influence of pulse duration, non-linearity of dosimeter response, energy and angular dependence were studied against the IEC 61674:2024 limits of variation. Energy response was tested using the standard RQR and RQT radiation qualities defined in IEC 61267:2005, as well as non-standard copper-filtered beams with added 0.9 mm Cu filtration. *Results:* Most dosimeters complied with the IEC 61674:2024 standard limits of variation, for both standard and non-standard radiation fields. In some cases, observed performance was significantly better than the current limits allowing for the introduction of more stringent values. *Conclusion:* Modification of the performance requirements was proposed, considering differences between reference-class and field-class dosimeters, while introducing more stringent requirements for reference-class dosimeters.

Keywords: *dosimeter response, ionization chamber, radiography, solid-state detector, X-ray multimeter*

3 Introduction

Frequency of medical imaging procedures in diagnostic and interventional radiology has increased with time, leading to a corresponding rise in the cumulative dose for the population. The purpose of diagnostic and interventional procedures is to produce medical images of satisfying quality while delivering patient doses as low as reasonably achievable (ALARA) [1, 2]. Many of the quality control (QC) tasks are performed through the measurement of the X-ray tube output in terms of air kerma (rate), either by in-house medical physicists or third-party dosimetry services. These data also provide the medical physicists with means to perform optimization of medical imaging procedures and patient doses. The use of fit for purpose high quality equipment (with reduced sensitivity to influence quantities) would improve accuracy of the acquired dosimetry data, which would have significant clinical implications by improving QC, optimizing diagnostic radiology procedures and reducing patient exposure. The goal of these activities is to ensure that clinical information of sufficient quality can be extracted, and patient doses can be optimized. The incident air kerma is one of metrics used as patient dose indicator in diagnostic radiology [3, 4], and it can be further used for patient dose estimations.

Ionization chambers (ICs) were commonly used for quality control of X-ray units in different modalities of medical X-ray imaging, including diagnostic and interventional radiography. Currently, quality control procedures related to dosimetry-based quantities and measurements can be performed either with ionization chambers or solid-state detectors, while for other QC tests different instruments are utilized (e.g., collimation/beam alignment test tools). Diagnostic radiology dosimeters which employ vented ionization chambers used for incident air kerma or air kerma rate measurements are usually realized either as spherical, cylindrical or plane-parallel detectors. Historically, plane-parallel ionization chambers were predominantly used for diagnostic radiology measurements (along with passive dosimeters and solid-state detectors), while spherical ionization chambers were usually designed for scattered radiation measurements [5]. Today, both plane-parallel and spherical ionization chambers are suitable for diagnostic radiology measurements due to their relatively constant response to variations in photon energy. Ionization chambers are commonly used with an associated electrometer measuring assembly.

X-ray multimeters (XMMs) are based on semiconductor detectors which enable simultaneous measurement of several quantities and parameters of interest, including air kerma, X-ray tube voltage, half-value layer (HVL), total filtration (TF), and other. Due to the possibility of measuring several quantities simultaneously, these devices are being more frequently used in QC procedures. XMMs are realized either as multi-element or single-element detectors, which are connected to a designated electrometer module (EMM) and display unit. These dosimeters can usually be used in a wide range of radiation conditions, since their performance is dependent on the incorporated manufacturer defined algorithm which compensates for energy dependence, with further adjustments of the associated software settings for each individual XMM. The design of XMM detector unit usually includes lead shielding, reducing the contribution of scattered radiation which originates from the objects and equipment in the clinical setup (e.g., patient table). Therefore, XMMs are designed to measure the incident air kerma instead of the entrance surface air kerma (ESAK), which includes backscattered radiation [6].

It is common practice that XMMs are adjusted by the manufacturers, based on the radiation conditions related to clinical needs of medical physicists, which are often not aligned with the standardized radiation fields used in

calibration laboratories. Adjustment of a measuring instrument represents a set of operations carried out on the device (e.g., the parameters of the implemented dose calculation algorithm) so that the displayed value corresponds to the measured value of a reference standard [7].

As an addition to manufacturer-specific XMM adjustment, standard dosimetry laboratories (abbreviated in the paper as SDLs, and including both primary standard - PSDLs and secondary standard - SSDLs) provide calibration services for these devices in standard radiation fields. Conditions under which dosimeter calibration is performed do not always correspond to the clinical settings, where the QC is performed. Calibration under reference conditions improves the quality of the dosimetry data by providing traceability to the relevant primary standard, ensuring good long-time stability and performance of the detectors and can help in identifying any malfunctions. Reference conditions for calibration and testing of diagnostic radiology dosimeters are defined in IEC 61267:2005 [8]. This standard was issued by the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) subcommittee 62C which deals with equipment used for radiotherapy, nuclear medicine and radiation dosimetry. The reference radiation conditions are described parametrically through X-ray tube voltage, first half-value layer and homogeneity coefficient. As per the IEC 61267:2005 standard, tube voltage and HVL values defined for many reference radiation conditions are non-nominal, so the additional filtration must be modified to achieve these values within stated tolerance (e.g., ratio of air kerma with absorber of HVL-equivalent thickness and with no absorber should be within 0.485 – 0.515) [8]. Reference radiation fields include aluminium filtered and copper filtered radiation qualities in general radiography.

Current technological advancements in medical imaging have led to the situation where the present IEC radiation conditions defined for radiography-based procedures are not well representative of the radiation fields encountered in clinical settings. Consequently, traceability needs to be established for non-standard radiation fields. Apart from diagnostic radiology, special consideration should be taken for interventional radiology procedures, due to their significant contribution to patient doses.

Previously conducted research addressed this matter through the development of two non-standard copper-filtered radiation qualities [9]. The properties of these radiation fields were determined based on the analysis of the manufacturer specifications of the X-ray generators used for interventional radiology and cardiology procedures. Based on the sample of 180 Radiation Dose Structured Reports, the most frequently added copper filtration thicknesses were 0.1, 0.3 and 0.9 mm Cu. Therefore, two radiation qualities which utilize the extreme value of 0.9 mm copper filtration were developed. XMM performance in these radiation fields was evaluated, relative to the standard radiation quality RQR8 (defined by 100 kV nominal voltage and 3.97 mm Al first HVL). The previously mentioned research highlighted the need for establishing new radiation qualities in calibration laboratories, which correspond to conditions encountered in clinical settings. Calibration of dosimeters in such radiation fields would improve the QC procedures by reducing the measurement uncertainty.

Hourdakis et al., [10] have investigated the performance of ICs and XMMs in reference radiation qualities under laboratory conditions and in the clinical radiation fields, with the goal of evaluating the influence of different exposure conditions on their response. They have observed that the IEC compliant dosimeters which are used in line with their manufacturer specifications can be used in clinical conditions, with the dose measurement error less than 3 % if adequate energy dependence corrections are applied in typical clinical conditions.

Research performed by [11] and [12] presented evaluation of XMMs and ICs performance across standard radiation quality series, covering a wide range of operating conditions encountered in diagnostic radiology. Versatility outside of manufacturer-stated specifications was investigated, highlighting the potential for use in diverse clinical environments.

Some of the previous research was focused on the performance of XMMs in mammography radiation fields, where it was concluded that these devices can be used for quality control in non-standard radiation fields due to observed low energy dependence of response in terms of air kerma for different anode/filtration setups. If these devices were to be used for quality control in conditions other than used for calibration, this should be considered in the measurement uncertainty budget [13-15].

This research has been conducted under the scope of the joint research project 22NRM01 TraMeXI: Traceability in Medical X-ray imaging dosimetry. The aims of this project consist of assessing currently available calibration procedures and the performance of dosimeters used in clinical applications, for the purpose of developing new and updated calibration procedures and implementing them into standards, guidelines and protocols.

In this paper the performance of ICs and XMMs for the measurement of air kerma was investigated, in terms of their response to different influence quantities, including energy dependence, angular dependence, non-linearity, dosimeter stabilization and repeatability and pulse duration. A comprehensive study emphasizing the performance of diagnostic dosimeters in standard radiation fields was done, considering the effect of several influence quantities on air kerma measurements with both reference class and field class dosimeters, as well as the performance of some dosimeters in non-standard copper filtered radiation fields. A proposal for changes in the limits of variation for different

influence quantities was given, as well as the differentiation between the requirements set for reference class and field class dosimeters was introduced. Implementation of proposed changes would impact the quality of acquired diagnostic dosimetry data, leading to better optimization of diagnostic radiology procedures and reduced patient doses.

4 Materials and methods

4.1 Radiation qualities

The IEC 61267:2005 [8] defines four distinct radiation quality series which describe primary X-ray beams in radiography. Aluminium filtered radiation qualities which are commonly used for dosimeter calibration in SDLs are abbreviated as RQR. These radiation qualities cover X-ray tube voltages from 40 to 150 kV with HVLs ranging from 1.42 to 6.57 mm Al (Table 1). Typically, diagnostic radiology dosimeters are calibrated in the RQR 5 and/or RQR 8 radiation qualities in conventional radiography [16] and RQR 5 is usually designated as the reference radiation quality [17]. It is important to stress that medical physicists in hospitals may use XMMs which have undergone certain adjustments by manufacturers, specific for their clinical needs, not complying with the standard reference radiation qualities. Besides the Al-filtered beams, two series of radiation qualities which utilize copper filtration are also defined in the standard. The RQT radiation quality series is defined in the X-ray tube voltage range from 100 kV to 150 kV with HVL values ranging from 6.9 to 10.1 mm Al and nominal added copper filtration ranging from 0.2 to 0.3 mm Cu, respectively (Table 1). The RQT radiation qualities are commonly used in SDL calibration procedures of pencil-type ionization chambers (abbreviated as CT-chambers) used for computerized tomography dosimetry. The RQC radiation quality series utilize large copper filtration (0.5 – 2.0 mm Cu) in the X-ray tube voltage range from 50 kV to 100 kV. These radiation fields are not commonly used for dosimeter calibration since they do not correspond well to the clinically used fields. Both RQT and RQC radiation qualities are established by adding a specific thickness of copper filtration to the corresponding RQR radiation qualities. For example, while both RQT 8 and RQC 8 have the same nominal voltage of 100 kV, the additional copper filtration for these radiation qualities is 0.2 and 2.0 mm Cu respectively. The copper filtration is added to the RQR 8 beam quality to realize the RQT 8 or RQC 8 beam qualities.

A market analysis of the available X-ray generators used for general and interventional radiography was performed under the scope of TraMeXI project, through the direct contact with the manufacturers and based on the manufacturer specifications, with the goal to propose new radiation qualities which more closely correspond to the clinical conditions. These radiation qualities would incorporate copper filtrations of thicknesses in the range from 0.1 mm Cu up to 0.9 mm Cu, updating the current set of RQC radiation qualities. Three of the new clinically relevant and physical representative radiation qualities (abbreviated as CPRQs) have been included in this study.

CPRQs used in this research, CPRQ 5, CPRQ 8 and CPRQ 9, are built upon the RQR 5, RQR 8 and RQR 9 beam qualities, by introducing additional 0.9 mm Cu filtration to the respective RQR radiation qualities. These radiation qualities were established by measuring the first and second HVLs and by comparing these values with the values generated by SpekPy Web (built on SpekPy v.2.0.8) [18-20]. First HVLs for these radiation qualities were determined according to the standard procedure described in the International Atomic Energy Agency Technical Report Series document, IAEA TRS 457 [17]. Comparison of parameters which describe RQR, RQT and RQC radiation quality series with selected CPRQs is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Properties of standard RQR, RQT, RQC [8] beam qualities and non-standard copper-filtered radiation qualities (CPRQ) used in this research, where RQ – radiation quality. Nominal values of aluminum and copper filter thickness are given, as well as the corresponding HVL values in terms of mm Al.

U (kV)	RQR [8]		RQT [8]		RQC [8]		CPRQ (non-standard)	
	RQ	HVL (mm Al)	RQ	HVL (mm Al)	RQ	HVL (mm Al)	RQ	HVL (mm Al)
40	RQR 2	1.42						
50	RQR 3	1.78			RQC 3	4.5		
60	RQR 4	2.19						
70	RQR 5	2.58			RQC 5	8.4	CPRQ 5	7.65
80	RQR 6	3.01						
90	RQR 7	3.48						
100	RQR 8	3.97	RQT 8	6.9	RQC 8	11.5	CPRQ 8	10.1
120	RQR 9	5.00	RQT 9	8.4			CPRQ 9	11.3
150	RQR 10	6.57	RQT 10	10.1				

For mammography applications, reference radiation conditions are defined for molybdenum (Mo) anode/filtration setup in the X-ray tube voltage range from 25 to 35 kV with respective HVL values ranging from 0.28 to 0.36 mm Al [8]. On the other hand, clinically encountered mammography X-ray generators utilize additional different anode/filtration setups (e.g., W/Ag, W/Rh, and other), expanding the HVL range for the same X-ray tube voltages up to approximately 0.6 mm Al [14,15].

4.2 Ionization chambers

A total of 16 ionization chambers were examined in this research, covering 7 different detector models from different manufacturers. The results were collected and evaluated by the Vinca Institute of Nuclear Sciences. The list of ionization chambers with associated dosimetry laboratories is presented in Table 2. Ionization chambers included in this study are the 3.6 cm³ spherical ionization chamber Exradin A3 (Standard Imaging) which is commonly used in dosimetry laboratories as a standard instrument for conventional radiography; the 3.46 cm³ Exradin Magna A650 (Standard Imaging) which is a plane-parallel ionization chamber used for both general radiography and mammography; the 6 cm³ 10X6-6 (Radcal) is a cylindrical ionization chamber used for a wide range of photon energies encompassing the range from 20 keV up to 1.25 MeV. The 6 cm³ RC6M (Radcal) plane-parallel ionization chamber is designated for mammography-specific low-energy X-ray measurements up to 40 keV. A thin-window plane-parallel 0.2 cm³ PTW 23344 (PTW) ionization chamber for low-energy X-ray radiotherapy calibrations was also included in the study. Even though this is a radiotherapy ionization chamber, according to the manufacturer specifications the chamber can be used in the energy range from 8 keV up to 35 keV. The other two plane-parallel ionization chambers included in this study are the 6 cm³ PTW 34069 and the 75 cm³ PTW 34060, which are used for absolute dosimetry in diagnostic radiology/mammography and diagnostic radiology, respectively. As per manufacturer specifications, these ionization chambers can be used in front of or behind a patient-equivalent phantom in diagnostic procedures.

Table 2. Ionization chambers included in the study, along with the respective dosimetry calibration laboratories (SDL).

IC model	Intended use	IC type	Active volume	IC No. (SDL)	Symbol
Exradin A3	radiography	spherical	3.6 cm ³	IC1 (CMI)	●
				IC2 (IMBiH)	●
				IC3 (EEAE)	●
				IC4 (PTB)	●
				IC5 (VSL)	●
Exradin Magna A650	mammography radiography	plane-parallel	3.46 cm ³	IC6 (ENEA)	★
Radcal RC6M	mammography	plane-parallel	6 cm ³	IC7 (CMI)	▲
				IC8 (ENEA)	▲
				IC9 (PTB)	▲
Radcal 10X6-6	radiography	cylindrical	6 cm ³	IC10 (STUK)	★
PTW 34069	mammography	plane-parallel	6 cm ³	IC11 (IMBiH)	◆
				IC12 (TENMAK)	◆
				IC13 (IST)	◆
PTW 34060	radiography	plane-parallel	75 cm ³	IC14 (TENMAK)	▶
				IC15 (ARPANSA)	▶
PTW 23344	superficial radiotherapy	plane-parallel	0.2 cm ³	IC16 (TENMAK)	■

4.3 X-ray multimeters

A total of 24 XMMs (9 dosimeter models) from different manufacturers were included in this study, including state-of-the-art dosimeter models, as well as some of the old previous models. In Table 3 the list of XMMs is provided, along with the respective manufacturer specifications in terms of air kerma (rate) measurements, and the calibration dosimetry laboratory.

Table 3. X-ray multimeters included in the study, their manufacturer specifications for air kerma (rate) measurements and the respective dosimetry calibration laboratory (SDL).

XMM	Air kerma (rate) range	Uncertainty	XMM No. (SDL)	Symbol
Raysafe X2 R/F	1 nGy·s ⁻¹ - 500 mGy·s ⁻¹ 1 nGy - 10 kGy	5%	XMM1 (ARPANSA)	▲
			XMM2 (IST)	▲
			XMM3 (STUK)	▲
			XMM4 (VINS)	▲
			XMM5 (UFPE)	▲
Raysafe Xi R/F	20 μGy·s ⁻¹ - 1 Gy·s ⁻¹ 10 μGy - 10 kGy	5%	XMM6 (STUK)	▼
			XMM7 (VINS)	▼
			XMM8 (EEAE)	▼
Raysafe ThinX RAD	0.1 mGy·s ⁻¹ - 100 mGy·s ⁻¹ 20 μGy - 1 Gy	5%	XMM9 (VINS)	★
RTI Piranha	10 μGy·s ⁻¹ - 450 mGy·s ⁻¹ 0.7 μGy - 1 kGy	5%	XMM10 (IST)	●
			XMM11 (VINS)	●
			XMM12 (UFPE)	●
			XMM13 (CMI)	●
			XMM14 (EEAE)	●
RTI Mako	1 nGy·s ⁻¹ - 500 mGy·s ⁻¹ 1 nGy - 10 kGy	5%	XMM15 (STUK)	★
PTW Nomex	5 μGy·s ⁻¹ - 500 mGy·s ⁻¹ 50 nGy - 500 Gy	3.5%	XMM16 (ARPANSA)	■
			XMM17 (INM)	■
Radcal AGMS-DM+ / AGMS-D+	40 nGy·s ⁻¹ - 200 mGy·s ⁻¹ 40 nGy - 100 Gy	5%	XMM18 (STUK)	◆
			XMM19 (ENEA)	◆
			XMM20 (UFPE)	◆
IBA MagicMax	100 nGy·s ⁻¹ - 160 mGy·s ⁻¹ 150 nGy - 50 Gy	5%	XMM21 (VSL)	▶
			XMM22 (PTB)	▶
Quart didoNEO	0.5 μGy·s ⁻¹ - 1 Gy·s ⁻¹ 1 μGy - 1 Gy	5%	XMM23 (VSL)	◆
			XMM24 (PTB)	◆

4.4 Dosimeter response and limits of variation

Performance of diagnostic radiology dosimeters is evaluated according to the IEC 61674:2024 standard [21], which defines the performance tests with associated compliance criteria expressed in terms of limits of variation. The dosimeter response is defined as the quotient of the indicated (measured) value by the diagnostic dosimeter under test and the conventional true value determined by the standard instrument (ionization chamber). If the deviation in the dosimeter response caused by variation of certain influence quantities is within certain test-dependent limits, compliance of the dosimeter with the standard is achieved. Testing of the effect of a certain influence quantity is performed while maintaining other influence quantities at their respective reference values (in line with the standard defined reference conditions), or by performing necessary corrections accounting for these effects. Relative response at a specific value of an influence quantity is derived by normalization of the response at that value to the response value determined for the reference conditions. During the tests with the XMMs, the reference values were defined by the SDL secondary or primary standard ionization chambers. On the other hand, performance tests of ICs presented in terms of response, were done by comparing the measured value with the reference value determined by the ionization chambers and free air chambers of the higher order in the metrological traceability chain.

5 Performance tests

5.1 Repeatability and resolution

Repeatability of the dosimeter indication was evaluated using the reference radiation quality RQR 5 for both XMMs and ICs. According to the standard [21] if the air kerma rate is equal to or greater than 100 μGy·s⁻¹ in the primary beam, the coefficient of variation should be less than or equal to 3%. This test was performed for three different situations: at the typical air kerma rate used for calibration; at the lower limit of air kerma rate, based on the capabilities of the SDLs; at the air kerma rate of 100 μGy·s⁻¹. It should be noted that for the dose rates less than 100 μGy·s⁻¹ in the unattenuated beam, the criterion can be more relaxed, up to 5 % (for e.g., 1 μGy·s⁻¹). At these dose rates the limit is dose rate dependent and determined with the equation presented in Table 3 of the standard [21].

Data on resolution of diagnostic dosimeters was collected during the repeatability test, as this property of the dosimeter represents an important limitation regarding measurement uncertainty. Resolution represents the smallest significant change in the dosimeter indication. Requirement on dosimeter resolution set by the standard is that the resolution should not be greater than 1% over the effective measurement range [21].

5.2 Dosimeter stabilization

The effect of stabilization time on the dosimeter indication was investigated by performing a series of measurement commencing with different time lapse intervals after the dosimeter is switched on. The time lapse intervals used were <1 min, ~15 min, ~30 min, ~45 min and ~60 min. The dosimeter is in compliance with the standard if the relative error is in agreement with the following condition:

$$\delta(\tau) = \frac{R(\tau) - R_{ref}}{R_{ref}} \leq L \quad (1)$$

where $R(\tau)$ represents the value of the dosimeter response after the certain time interval, R_{ref} is the response reference value at 60 min (approximation of steady state), and L is the $\pm 2\%$ limit of variation, as defined by the IEC standard [21].

5.3 Linearity of the response

Response linearity of ICs and XMMs in terms of air kerma rate measurements was examined in a wide range of dose rate values, where the selected values were dependent on the capabilities of each SDL. The dose rate ranged from $5 \mu\text{Gy}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ up to $0.1 \text{ Gy}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ with reference air kerma rate being $0.5 \text{ mGy}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. A diagnostic dosimeter is compliant with the standard if its highest and lowest response values over the tested dose rate range fulfil the following condition:

$$\frac{R_{max} - R_{min}}{R_{max} + R_{min}} \leq L \quad (2)$$

where R_{max} and R_{min} represent the maximum and minimum values of the dosimeter response determined over the whole test range, and L represents the limit of variation of $\pm 2\%$ [21].

5.4 Variation in response due to photon energy

Exposure of diagnostic radiology dosimeters to radiation fields in clinical settings may differ from the standard defined reference radiation qualities established in dosimetry calibration laboratories. The changes in the incident X-ray spectra (caused either by the changes in incident beam primary filtration, or the X-ray tube voltage) can lead to variation in dosimeter response. In general, the effect of energy dependence of dosimeter response is more pronounced with solid-state detectors compared to ICs. XMMs, being based on solid-state detectors, usually have sets of filters and manufacturer-defined software corrections to compensate for variations in beam energies. In some cases, user input is needed (e.g. to select tube voltage range, or to select target/filter combination for mammography applications).

The energy dependence of ICs and XMMs was examined by determining the relative energy response, normalized to the reference radiation quality RQR 5 for all radiation quality series used in the tests. The test was performed using the RQR and RQT series of radiation qualities [8]. In some of the SDLs the performance of dosimeters was also evaluated in the non-standard radiation fields. The traceability of the reference value (see equation (3)) was obtained either through direct traceability to the primary standard or by performing HVL-based interpolation of the secondary standard calibration coefficient.

Relative energy response of the dosimeters is defined by the following equation:

$$r(E) = \frac{R(E)}{R_0(E_0)} = \frac{M(E)/K_R(E)}{M(E_0)/K_R(E_0)} \quad (3)$$

where R represents the dosimeter response at a certain radiation quality E , and R_0 is the response at the reference radiation quality E_0 . K_R represents the reference air kerma, while M is the measured value. The limits of variation for the relative energy response are set to $\pm 5\%$ for the radiation qualities in the range from RQR 3 (50 kV) to RQR 10 (150 kV) [21], while the RQR 2 is not included in the rated range.

For mammography specific ionization chambers (IC6, IC7, IC8 and IC9) the energy dependence of response was evaluated in the X-ray tube voltage range from 25 kV to 35 kV, for each of the anode/filtration setups separately, by normalizing the response to the respective reference response at 28 kV. Available anode/filtration setups are different between dosimetry calibration laboratories. Relative response limits of variation are set to $\pm 5\%$ for each anode/filtration setup [21].

5.5 Variation in response due to angle of incidence

Angular dependence of dosimeter response was tested in two perpendicular planes (horizontal and vertical dosimeter orientation, as shown in Fig. 1) by performing rotations in both directions, within the rated range, up to the angle of incidence of $\pm 5^\circ$. The variation in response was evaluated by performing normalization to the response at 0° . Limits of variation of $\pm 3\%$ are defined in the standard for the minimum rated range [21].

Besides testing in these two dosimeter orientations, the effect of dosimeter rotation was also evaluated. For this test, angles from 0° to 360° were used, with the dosimeter facing the X-ray source over the whole duration of the test, Fig.1. Normalization of dosimeter response relative to the response at 0° was performed. Dosimeter rotation test is not included in the current version of the standard for air kerma measurement [21]. Although, this effect is considered as of the tests defined in the standard related to measurement of X-ray tube voltage with non-invasive instruments, IEC 61676:2023 [22].

Figure 1. Setup for the angular dependence test in two dosimeter orientations (left and middle) and the effect of rotation (right), where N represents angle of incidence.

5.6 Effect of pulse duration

Variation of the dosimeter response due to the effect of pulsed radiation was examined by two SDLs (VSL and PTB). Pulse duration was varied from 200 ms up to 20 s, where the selected reference pulse duration was 10 s [23]. The minimum pulse duration defined in the IEC standard [21] of 1 ms was not included in this study due to the limitations of the laboratory X-ray generators. The limits of variation for this effect are defined in the same manner as for the linearity test (Section 3.3).

6 Results

Properties of diagnostic radiology dosimeters for the measurement of air kerma (rate) were evaluated by performing several performance tests following the compliance tests defined by IEC 61674:2024 [21], in terms of limits of variation of dosimeter response. Legends in all figures were listed in Table 2 for ICs and Table 3 for XMMs.

It was ensured by each SDL that the requirements on the number of measurements were fulfilled for each test that was performed. Minimum number of measurements needed was determined based on the requirements from IEC 61674 [21], which consider the coefficient of variation with respect to the limits of variation.

6.1 Repeatability and resolution

At the typical air kerma rate used for dosimeter calibration in the dosimetry laboratory practice, the maximum values of the coefficients of variation of 0.3% and 0.9% were recorded for ICs and XMMs, respectively. For the dose rate of $100 \mu\text{Gy}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, the largest coefficient of variation observed was 0.6% for ICs and 0.2% for XMMs. These values fulfil the IEC criteria [21], where the limit for the coefficient of variation for the unattenuated beam is set at 3%. In the case of the lowest air kerma rate available in the diagnostic radiology calibration facilities, maximum coefficients of variation of 2.3% (for ICs) and 0.9% (for XMMs) were observed, for the respective air kerma rate of $5 \mu\text{Gy}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ and $1 \mu\text{Gy}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$.

Resolution of the ICs and XMMs depends on the properties of the associated electrometer. For the tested ICs, resolution of 0.5% or below was observed, based on the used electrometer manufacturer specifications. Selected XMMs were in line with the 1% requirement prescribed by the standard [21] for resolution in their respective effective ranges of indicated values.

6.2 Dosimeter stabilization

Deviation of dosimeter indication related to stabilization time is presented in Fig. 2 for both ICs and XMMs. It can be observed that both dosimeter types exhibit reduction in relative error in comparison to the error at the time τ , where $\tau < 1$ min. All the tested devices have deviations of their indication within $\pm 2\%$, complying with the IEC criteria [21]. The time stabilization property depends on the unit under test rather than the dosimeter type. Overall, ICs display more converging results compared to XMMs with time.

Figure 2. Relative error of diagnostic dosimeter measured value due to the effect of stabilization time (τ) for ionization chambers (a) and X-ray multimeters (b). Measured values were compared with indication measured at $\tau_0 = 60$ min.

6.3 Linearity of the response

From Fig. 3, it can be observed that the variation of the ionization chamber responses is within $\pm 1\%$ for a wide range of dose rates. In the case of XMMs (Fig. 4) this effect is more pronounced for some tested units. The majority of XMMs performed well, displaying relative response within $\pm 2\%$ if the outlier dosimeter units are excluded. Compared to the ICs, XMMs exhibited more pronounced non-linearity over a wide range of air kerma rates.

If the maximum and minimum response values for each dosimeter unit are examined against the criterion described in the standard [21], all the ICs in the study fulfilled the criterion defined by equation (2) with variation of response lower than 0.5% (criterion is 2%). Most of the XMM models fulfilled the requirement prescribed by the standard [21], except for XMM21 and XMM14, whose variation of response is 3.1% and 5.4% respectively.

Figure 3. Variation in ionization chamber relative response as a function of air kerma rate, normalized to the $0.5 \text{ mGy}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ reference air kerma rate, in the RQR 5 reference radiation field.

Figure 4. Variation in X-ray multimeter relative response as a function of air kerma rate, normalized to the $0.5 \text{ mGy}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ reference air kerma rate, in the RQR 5 reference radiation field: a) XMM1 – XMM11; b) XMM13 – XMM24.

6.4 Variation in response due to photon energy

Results on dosimeter performance in terms of relative energy response are presented in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 for ICs and XMMs respectively for RQR and RQT radiation qualities [8]. Responses of dosimeters in the selected CPRQ non-standard radiation fields are presented in Fig. 7.

Figure 6. Energy dependence of X-ray multimeter response, in terms of relative response normalized to the reference radiation quality RQR 5 [8]: a) XMM1 – XMM6; b) XMM7 – XMM12; c) XMM13 – XMM18; d) XMM19 – XMM24.

Fig. 7 shows the performance of five XMM models and one IC evaluated in the non-standard copper filtered radiation qualities (CPRQs), presented in Section 2.1. The 0.9 mm Cu radiation qualities were selected for performance assessment in terms of energy response, as the most heavily filtered primary beams encountered in clinical conditions. As with the RQR and RQT series, the response of the dosimeters was normalized to the RQR 5 radiation quality. The dosimeters tested were XMM4, XMM7 and XMM11 in VINS SDL, and XMM21, XMM23 and IC5 in VSL SDL. The response of IC5 deviated less than 0.6 % for all three CPRQ radiation qualities when compared to reference radiation quality. Measurement uncertainties for only one of the devices examined in PSDL and one of the devices examined in SSDL are displayed for clarity purposes.

Figure 7. Relative energy response of XMMs and IC in the non-standard copper-filtered radiation qualities with added filtration of 0.9 mm Cu to the RQR 5, RQR 8 and RQR 9 radiation qualities, compared with the IEC limit [21].

6.5 Uncertainty assessment in non-standard CPRQ radiation fields

The XMMs were examined in one PSDL and one SSDL, where the reference values in the non-standard radiation fields were obtained differently. In case of the PSDL, regular procedures were used and reference values were obtained using a primary standard, resulting in usual measurement uncertainties – 0.92% ($k = 2$). In case of the SSDL, calibration coefficients for the secondary standard were not available for some non-standard radiation qualities, and they were obtained by interpolation, which introduced additional measurement uncertainty. SSDL stated uncertainty is between 1.4% (CPRQ9) and 1.6% (CPRQ6) ($k = 2$).

6.6 Variation in response due to angle of incidence

Angular response performance test results are presented in Table 4. Angular dependence of responses in both horizontal and vertical orientation of dosimeters agree with the IEC standard in the minimum rated range, being within $\pm 3\%$ limits of variation [21]. The maximum deviation of -1.2% was observed for XMM12 at -5° , and -1.1% for XMM18 at $+5^\circ$, for horizontal and vertical orientations, respectively. Although, it was observed that most devices displayed angular dependence within $\pm 1\%$.

Table 4. Relative angular response of tested ICs and XMMs in the minimum rated range for vertical (V) and horizontal (H) dosimeter orientation.

Dosimeter	V (-5°)	V (+5°)	H (-5°)	H (+5°)
	Relative deviation [%]			
IC12	-0.10	-0.01	-0.01	-0.10
IC14	-0.01	-0.12	0.03	0.01
XMM1	/	/	0.09	-0.02
XMM3	0.18	-0.14	0.34	0.10
XMM5	/	/	0.10	-0.08
XMM6	0.49	-0.14	0.03	-0.20
XMM12	/	/	-1.23	0.15
XMM16	/	/	0.05	0.06
XMM17	0.11	0.13	-0.06	-0.10
XMM18	-0.83	-1.12	-0.92	-0.53
XMM20	/	/	-0.78	-0.21

Even though the IEC standard for air kerma measurements [21] does not provide any requirements on dosimeter rotation around the beam axis, this effect was examined following the requirements in the IEC 61676:2023 standard for tube voltage measurements [22]. The results of rotation performance test are presented in Table 5. Overall, the XMMs displayed relative error of indication within $\pm 0.5\%$ for all angles of rotation with respect to the 0° value.

Table 5. Relative error of indication for rotation of XMMs with respect to the 0° value

Dosimeter	45°	90°	135°	180°	225°	270°	315°
	Relative error [%]						
XMM3	0	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.2
XMM6	/	-0.4	/	0	/	0.5	/
XMM17	/	-0.1	/	0	/	-0.1	/
XMM18	-0.1	-0.2	-0.2	-0.3	-0.3	-0.2	0
XMM22	/	0.5	/	0.5	/	0.2	/
XMM24	/	-0.1	/	-0.1	/	-0.1	/

6.7 Effect of pulse duration

Effect of pulsed radiation is presented in Fig. 8. Performance of the diagnostic radiology dosimeters was evaluated in radiation fields of different pulse durations. Observed relative errors for IC4 were 0.14% at 1 s pulse duration, increasing to 0.41% at 200 ms pulse, respectively. The reduction in pulse duration led to the increase in variation of indication to $>1.5\%$ and up to 1.7% for XMM21, XMM23 and XMM24. On the other hand, XMM22 displayed minimal variation in indicated value, less than 0.05% for all pulse durations.

Figure 8. Variation in diagnostic dosimeter response due to the effect of pulsed radiation, normalized to 10000 ms pulse duration.

7 Discussion

7.1 Evaluation of dosimeter performance

The performance test results conducted in this research are presented in sections 4.1 – 4.6. The IEC 61674:2024 [21] requirements on dosimeter performance are currently set for diagnostic dosimeters with no distinction between field-class (XMMs) and reference-class dosimeters (ICs). Based on the test results it was determined that in most cases the acceptability criteria can be more stringent for reference-class dosimeters and in some cases for field-class dosimeters as well. The largest difference between reference- and field-class dosimeters was found in the energy dependence of the response. Therefore, more detailed discussion on this topic is provided.

7.2 Energy dependence of response

For 9 out of 11 ICs included in this test, the variation in the energy response was within $\pm 1\%$ over the whole energy range tested as shown in Fig. 5. The relative response of most XMMs in our study were within the $\pm 5\%$ limit defined by the IEC standard [21] both in standard and non-standard radiation qualities as shown in Fig. 6. The presented findings are in line with the results from previous research focused on diagnostic dosimeter performance in standard radiation fields [10-12].

For the non-standard copper-filtered beams (CPRQs) significant differences in the PSDL and SSDL measurement uncertainty of the reference value were observed as shown in Fig. 7. The air kerma rate measurement uncertainties for the CPRQs established in PSDL were similar to those for the standard radiation qualities, due to direct traceability to the primary standard, while the SSDL uncertainties were somewhat larger due to HVL-based interpolation of the secondary standard calibration coefficient. Examined XMMs have overall satisfactory performance in a wide range of photon energies, encompassing different medical imaging practices in general radiography and computerized tomography. Behavior of XMMs in copper-filtered radiation fields was in line with the previous research done within the VERIDIC project. XMMs which were evaluated in non-standard copper filtered beams (with 2.1 mm Al and 0.9 mm Cu), similar to CPRQs in this study, have also exhibited relative response within $\pm 5\%$, relative to RQR8 [9]. Energy compensation of XMM detectors is at least partly achieved by software corrections and/or user inputs, so incorrect settings could potentially produce erroneous data [14].

Further study of the added copper filtration influence on the dosimeter response is under preparation, including a wider range of proposed non-standard CPRQs, as this research shows promising results in terms of dosimeter performance in some of the non-standard radiation fields. The study will also be expanded to include a greater number of different XMMs, using these new radiation fields upon their establishment in a larger number of SDLs and to include other quantities besides air kerma.

Based on the existing results presented in this study, the IEC standard requirements for energy dependence of response could be decreased for the reference-class dosimeters from 5% to 1.5% or even lower. For field-class dosimeters, it should be kept at 5 % level, but the tested range could be extended to cover a larger range of clinically relevant radiation qualities.

7.3 Update of the IEC 61764 standard requirements

For most of the other influence quantities that were investigated, the IEC standard limits of variation could be decreased for both reference-class dosimeters (ICs) and field-class dosimeters (XMMs). The current IEC criteria for dosimeter response to influence quantities, as well as the proposed changes to these criteria for both reference-class and field-class dosimeters are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Proposed performance criteria for reference-class and field-class dosimeters for different influence quantities.

Influence quantity	IEC stated limits of variation [%] [21]	Proposed limits of variation [%]	
		Field-class dosimeters	Reference-class dosimeters
Repeatability	3	1*	1*
Time Stabilization	2	0.5	0.5
Resolution	1	0.5	0.5
Linearity	2	2	1
Energy Dependence	5	5	1.5
Angular Dependence	3	1	1
Rotation	-	0.5	0.5

*Proposed criteria for repeatability should remain the same for the dose rates below 100 $\mu\text{Gy}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$.

It should be kept in mind that there are limited capabilities of calibration and testing laboratories to achieve sufficiently low measurement uncertainties, to perform tests within these reduced limits. In general, according to the IEC standard, the overall measurement uncertainty (expanded uncertainty with the confidence level of 95%) should be less than one fifth of the limit of variation for a given test. In case that the uncertainty is greater than one fifth of the limit of variation and less than one half of the limit, the limit is expanded by the uncertainty [21]. The required uncertainties are achievable by most primary laboratories. In case of secondary laboratories, uncertainty analysis should be performed (including correlations), to make sure that the overall uncertainty is not larger than half of the limit. The change in limits would not affect routine calibrations, but only type testing of the dosimeters.

The 3% repeatability criteria could be more rigid and set to 1% for both ICs and XMMs for dose rates equal to or above 100 $\mu\text{Gy}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. For dose rates below this value the proposed limits should remain dose rate dependent. The requirement on dosimeter stabilization time of 2% could be significantly decreased for both ICs and XMMs. Based on the presented results (Fig. 2), the relative error of indication was less than $\pm 0.5\%$ for $\tau < 1$ min, with the reduction in error as stabilization time, τ is increased. The proposed limits of variation for time stabilization could be reduced to 0.5 % for both reference-class and field-class dosimeters. The 1% requirement for resolution could be decreased to 0.5%, based on the properties of the dosimeters used in practice. Linearity requirement of 2% on dosimeter response could remain unchanged for field-class dosimeters but for reference-class dosimeters this could be slightly lowered to 1% based on the results presented in Figs. 3 and 4.

The influence of angle of incidence in both horizontal and vertical planes can be considered negligible for most spherical and cylindrical ionization chambers, therefore the criteria for the reference-class dosimeters on these influence quantities can be negligible. However, since plane-parallel ICs are commonly used as well, the requirement could be set

to ~1%. In the case of XMMs, the requirement for angular dependence could be tightened from 3% to 1%, considering the minimum rated range of $\pm 5^\circ$ for angle of incidence and as indicated by the results shown in Table 4. The IEC requirement for dosimeter rotation is not currently defined in IEC 61674 [21], but the 0.5% limit proposed in IEC 61676:2023 for tube voltage measurements could also be applied for air kerma measurements and considered in future update of IEC 61674 standard following the results shown in Table 5. In the case of reference-class dosimeters this effect is negligible for general radiography. The angular dependence was further studied at STUK SSDL with an expanded range of tilting angles and XMMs, and those results support the recommendations given here [24].

The requirement on dosimeter response due to varying pulse duration is not explicitly specified in the standard, referencing to the criteria set for response linearity of 2 %. As the data shown in Fig. 8 is limited, a proposal to modify this requirement would require further testing with a larger sample of dosimeters and a wider range of pulse durations introduced to the test.

8 Conclusion

Response of the tested diagnostic dosimeters to specific influence quantities complies with the IEC 61674:2024 [21] requirements for most of the devices in all conducted performance tests. Most of the dosimeters behaved in an expected manner compared to limits of variation for stabilization time, dosimeter indication repeatability, response non-linearity, energy dependence, angular dependence and pulse duration. New performance criteria have been proposed to address the differences in field-class and reference-class dosimeters and extended to cover pulse duration and dosimeter rotation tests.

Introduction of new copper-filtered radiation qualities (CPRQs) allows testing of dosimeter performance in new radiation conditions that are more relevant to clinical practice. Calibration in such radiation fields might still not be the most appropriate approach due to large variety of clinical conditions, although in the event of calibration using these radiation fields the overall measurement uncertainty would be improved due to improved traceability. Establishing direct traceability for the proposed CPRQ copper-filtered radiation qualities would enable direct calibration of the secondary standards and end-user diagnostic dosimeters, reducing any errors in eventual interpolations in the clinical beams.

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